

Screening Of Bio-Pesticides against Pest of Cauliflower Thrip under the Climatic Condition of Tandojam, Sindh Pakistan

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Abstract

A field study was carried out during the year of 2017-18 at the experimental station of Entomology Section, Agriculture Research Institute, (ARI) Tandojam Sindh Pakistan so as to examine the efficacy of different bio-pesticides against cauliflower thrips. Seven treatments with three replications were applied. The treatments were: T1=chemical control (Confidor), T2=Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), T3=Akk (*Calotropis procera* Alton. F.), T4=Tooh (*Citrullus colocynthus* Schrad. L.), T5=*Datura* (*Datura stramonium*) T6=Tabacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) and T7=Control (untreated). One insect was found in the infesting cauliflower, for instance, thrips. Pre and post-treatment observations were also recorded. The results revealed that against thrips the first spray of chemical control (Confidor) showed highest efficacy (82.82%), followed by Neem extract (78.42%), Tobacco extract (72.33%), Tooh extract (69.51%), Akk extract (65.55%) and lowest for *Datura* extract (58.97%); while in the second spray also, chemical control (Confidor) showed the highest efficacy against thrips (88.35%); followed by Neem extract (85.39%), Tobacco extract (82.68%), Tooh extract (80.64%) and least by *Datura* extract (78.97%). According to the efficacy the treatments ranked as a synthetic pesticide (chemical control) Neem extract, Tobacco extract, Tooh extract, Akk extract, and *Datura* extract respectively. Although, the chemical control was effective against the cauliflower thrips, on the basis of efficacy, Neem extract, shows nearly effect followed by Tobacco extract and Tooh extract should be suggested for safe control of cauliflower thrips and having a less residual effect.

Keywords: Bio-pesticides, Cauliflower, Thrips, Sindh, Pakistan.

Introduction

Cauliflower, *Brassica oleracea* L. belongs to the family Cruciferae, is an annual plant that reproduces by seed. Typically, only the head (the white curd) of aborted floral meristems is eaten, while the stalk and surrounding thick, green leaves are used in vegetable broth or discarded. Its name is from Latin *caulis* (cabbage) and flower an acknowledgment of its unusual place among a family of food plants which normally produces only leafy greens for eating (Barbara, 1996). *Brassica oleracea* also includes cabbage, Brussels sprouts, kale, broccoli, and collard greens, though they are of different cultivar groups. Cauliflower can be roasted, boiled, fried, steamed or eaten raw. Steaming or microwaving better preserves anticancer compounds than boiling. When cooking, the outer leaves and thick stalks are removed, leaving only the florets. The leaves are also edible but are most often discarded (Stephens, 1998).

Cauliflower crop is attacked by a number of insect pests which include root maggots, cutworms, aphids, harlequin bugs, flea beetles, cabbage worms and loppers. Synthetic insecticides are widely used in most developing countries to control these insect pests. This has contributed to the environmental pollution through the air or as residues in food. In the last years, the use of environmentally bio-pesticides, such as plant extracts widely increased. The diverse biological activities of bio-pesticides (plant extracts) include feeding and oviposition deterrence, repellence, growth disruption, reduced fitness, and sterility (Schmutterer, 1990).

Therefore, the present study was carried out to screen out plant extracts being used as bio-pesticides against the pest (thrips) on cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* L.) at the climatic condition of Tandojam, Sindh Pakistan.

Following were the specific objectives of the study.

Objectives

1. To examine the efficacy of different bio-pesticides against cauliflower thrips.
2. To suggest most effective bio-pesticide against cauliflower thrips.

Materials and methods

A field experiment on the screening of bio-pesticides (plant extracts) and Confidor against the cauliflower thrips was conducted during the year of 2017-18. The experiment was designed in a three replicated Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with sub-plot size of 3m² (3m x 3m). The sowing dates and methods were observed according to the plan of work. The recommended planting rate of 5.0 kg ha⁻¹ was applied; whereas row to row distance of 60 cm and plant to plant distance of 15 cm was maintained. The seed of cauliflower variety Thori-78 was used throughout the experiment. The extracts of the following botanicals plants were used to investigate their efficacy against cauliflower thrips. There were seven treatments show below:

- T1** Chemical control (Confidor)
- T2** Neem (*Azadirachta indica*)
- T3** Akk (*Calotropis procera* Alton. F.)
- T4** Tooh (*Citrullus colocynthus* Schrad. L.)
- T5** Datura (*Datura stramonium*)
- T6** Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*)
- T7** Control (untreated)

For the preparation of plant extract, 10 kg leaves each of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*), Akk (*Calotropis procera* Alton. F.), Tooh (*Citrullus colocynthus* Schrad. L.) and Datura (*Datura stramonium*) were collected and processed for getting the extract. Each treatments stock weight was 10 kg boiled in 10 liters of water. The leaves of each plant species were taken separately and filtered through muslin cloth. When water remained, 5 liters stock solution was ready to spray. After preparing the extracts, the cauliflower plants were sprayed with a knapsack hand sprayer. In all two sprays were carried out, and the efficacy was examined after 24, 48, 72, 96 hours 1 week and 2 weeks of spray and compared with control. Recommended pesticide for cauliflower was sprayed for chemical control (confider) @ 250 ml / acre (0.56ml/plot) and biopesticide 5liter/Acr (12ml/plot) was sprayed. The data thus collected were subjected to statistical analysis by using the analysis of variance so as to know the significance of differences in the population of thrips and infestation at different intervals after treatment. The LSD (Least Significance Difference) test was also applied in order to compare the different treatments for their efficacies against thrips pest.

Results

1st spray

Statistically, the differences in thrips population on cauliflower plantation were non-significant for pre-treatment (F=0.02; DF=20; P>0.05), 24 hours after first spray (F=0.65; DF=20; P>0.05), 48 hours after first spray (F=1.25; DF=20; P>0.05) and 72 hours after first spray (F=2.02; DF=20; P>0.05); while thrips population decreased significantly after 96 hours of first spray (F=2.92; DF=20; P<0.05); after one week of first spray (F=7.25; DF=20; P<0.05) and two weeks after first spray (F=10.93; DF=20; P<0.05).

Table-1 Efficacy of various bio-pesticides against thrips infestation on cauliflower as compared to chemical control (Confidor) at different intervals after the first spray.

Plant extracts	Pre-treatment	Post treatment observation/plant after:						Pest Reduction /plant	Reduction %
		24hrs	48hrs	72hrs	96hrs	1week	2week		
Chemical control (confidor)	12.47	9.47	8.15	7.01	6.03	3.51	2.14	10.32	82.82
Neem extract	12.33	9.62	8.66	7.79	7.01	3.86	2.66	9.67	78.42
Akk extract	12.22	10.14	9.53	8.96	8.42	5.19	4.21	8.01	65.55
Tooh extract	12.67	10.39	9.66	8.98	8.35	4.95	3.86	8.80	69.51
Dhatura extract	12.13	10.31	9.90	9.50	9.12	5.86	4.98	7.16	58.97
Tobacco extract	12.13	9.71	8.93	8.22	7.56	4.48	3.36	8.78	72.33
Untreated	12.33	12.46	12.33	12.21	12.09	11.97	11.85	0.49	3.95
S.E.±	0.3989	0.2887	0.2250	0.1842	0.1902	0.1093	0.1298		
LSD 0.05	0.8692	0.6290	0.4903	0.4013	0.4144	0.2381	0.2813		
LSD 0.01	1.2185	0.8818	0.6873	0.5626	0.5810	0.3338	0.3943		

Significant level 0.05

The effect of bio-pesticides (Table-1) indicated that in cauliflower plantation sprayed with Chemical control (Cofidor), the thrips population reduced from 12.47/leaf to 2.14/leaf after two weeks of spray indicating the highest efficacy of 82.82%; while the crop sprayed with the biopesticide Neem extract ranked 2nd, where pre-treatment thrips population of 12.33/leaf decreased to 2.66/leaf after 2 weeks of spray showing efficacy of 78.42 percent. The crop sprayed with tobacco extract ranked 3rd, where pre-treatment thrips population of 12.13/leaf decreased to 3.36/leaf after 2 weeks of spray showing the efficacy of 72.33%. The cauliflower plantation treated with Tooh ranked 4th, where pre-treatment thrips population of 12.67/leaf decreased to 3.86/leaf after 2 weeks of spray showing the efficacy of 69.51%. The Akk extract ranked 5th, where pre-treatment thrips population of 12.22/leaf decreased to 4.21/leaf after 2 weeks of spray showing the efficacy of 65.55%. Similarly, the spraying of Dhatura extracts ranked 6th, where pre-treatment thrips population of 12.13/leaf decreased to 4.98/leaf after 2 weeks of spray with the lowest efficacy of 58.97%. According to the efficacy, the treatments ranking was Neem extract, chemical control, tobacco extract, Tooh extract, Akk extract, and Dhatura extract respectively.

2nd spray

Thrips population on cauliflower after second spray of bio-pesticides showed non-significant variation for pre-treatment (F=0.44; DF=20; P>0.05) and when monitored after 24 hours of spray (F=1.39; DF=20; P>0.05); while the thrips population declined significantly when monitored after 48 hours of spray (F=5.02; DF=20; P<0.05), 72 hours after spray (F=9.69; DF=20; P<0.05), 96 hours after spray (F=12.81; DF=20; P<0.05); one week after spray (F=170.60; DF=20; P<0.05) and two weeks after spray (F=129.05; DF=20; P<0.05).

Table-2 Efficacy of various bio-pesticides against thrips infestation on cauliflower as compared to chemical control (Confidor) at different intervals after the second spray.

Plant extracts	Pre-treatment	Post treatment observation/plant after:						Pest Reduction /plant	Reduction %
		24hrs	48hrs	72hrs	96hrs	1week	2week		
Chemical control (confidor)	8.22	5.75	4.37	3.57	3.19	0.96	0.89	7.26	88.35
Neem extract	8.00	5.68	4.43	3.71	3.34	1.17	1.15	6.83	85.39
Akk extract	7.82	6.02	5.06	4.40	4.09	1.63	2.01	6.18	79.09
Tooh extract	6.70	5.09	4.18	3.60	3.33	1.30	1.60	5.40	80.64
Dhatura extract	7.60	6.08	5.23	4.70	3.81	1.60	1.97	6.00	78.97
Tobacco extract	7.90	5.85	4.68	4.02	3.70	1.37	1.68	6.53	82.68
Untreated	7.27	7.34	7.27	7.19	7.12	7.05	6.98	0.22	2.98
S.E.±	1.0981	0.8205	0.6658	0.5812	0.5438	0.2353	0.2606		
LSD 0.05	2.3825	1.7877	1.4506	1.2663	1.1848	0.5127	0.5679		
LSD 0.01	3.3541	2.5062	2.0337	1.7753	1.6610	0.7188	0.7961		

Significant level 0.05

The data (Table-2) showed that the thrips population after second spray of synthetic pesticide (chemical control) reduced from 8.22/leaf to 0.89/leaf after two weeks of spray showing the highest efficacy of 88.35%; and the crop sprayed with neem extract ranked 2nd, where the thrips population decreased from 8.00/leaf to 1.15/leaf after 2 weeks of spray showing efficacy of 78.97%. The tobacco extract ranked 3rd, where the thrips population decreased from 7.90/leaf to 1.68/leaf after two weeks of spray, showing the efficacy of 82.68 %. Tooh extract ranked 4th, where thrips population decreased from 6.70/leaf to 1.60/leaf after two weeks of spray showing the efficacy of 80.64 %. Akk extract ranked 5th, where the thrips population decreased from 7.82/leaf to 2.01/leaf after 2 weeks of spray showing the efficacy of 79.09 %. Similarly, the spraying of Dhatura extracts ranked 6th, where pre-treatment thrips population of 7.60/leaf decreased to 1.97/leaf after 2 weeks of spray with the lowest efficacy of 78.97 %. According to the efficacy the treatments ranked as synthetic pesticide (chemical control) Neem extract, tobacco extract, Tooh extract, Akk extract, and Dhatura extract respectively.

Discussion

Recent research has proved that safe and Long- lasting solution of the thrips problem was associated with the use of natural substances for their control because nature has a balanced ecosystem that keeps the population of all the biological organisms within the specific limits being useful or harmful for other organisms on earth. The plant extracts are effective to control crop insect pests, and their application is safe for the human and other biological life. This study has entailed the screening of bio-pesticides against the cauliflower thrips.

The present study showed that against thrips the first spray of chemical control (Confidor) showed the highest efficacy of 82.82%, followed by Neem extract 78.42%, tobacco extract 72.33%, Tooh extract 69.51%, Akk extract 65.55% and lowest for Dhatura extract 58.97%; while in the second spray also, chemical control showed the highest efficacy against thrips 88.35%; followed by Neem extract 78.97%, tobacco extract 82.68%, Tooh extract 80.64% and least by Dhatura extract 78.97%.

While Shukla, A. and A. Kumar. 2006 reported that Neem seed kernel extract was effective in controlling insect pests with the highest cost: benefit ratio. Rukhsana *et al.*, (2010) reported that among the plant material, best antifungal activity was achieved by extracts of *Azadirachta indica* (Neem), and *Allium sativum* (garlic) at the concentration of 0.015%. Ahuja *et al.*, 2012; Nzanza and Mashela (2012) reported that the mixture of Neem

and wild garlic was more effective in reducing population densities of whitefly and aphid than either plant extract applied alone. In conclusion, the results of this study suggested a synergistic effect of fermented plant extracts of Neem and wild garlic as a bio-pesticide.

Conclusions and suggestions

The results showed that against thrips the first spray of chemical control (Confidor) showed the highest efficacy 82.82%, followed by Neem extract with efficacy of 78.42 %; tobacco extract with efficacy of 72.33%, Tooh with efficacy of 69.51%, Akk extract with efficacy of 65.55%, and Dhatura extract resulted in lowest efficacy against thrips 58.97%. The chemical control efficacy against cauliflower thrips after the second spray was also highest 88.35%, followed by Neem extract 85.39%, tobacco extract 82.68%, Tooh extract 80.64%, and Dhatura extract showed the least efficacy 78.97% against thrips after the second spray. However, the chemical pesticides were highly effective to control thrips on cauliflower; but Neem extract showed nearly relate results for its efficacy against the target pests when compared with chemical control. Further, the tobacco extract and Tooh extract also showed remarkable results for their efficacy against cauliflower thrips during both sprays. Based on the findings the following suggestion put forward. Although, the chemical control was effective against the cauliflower thrips, on the basis of efficacy, Neem extract, shows nearly effect followed by tobacco extract and Tooh extract should be suggested for safe control of cauliflower thrips and having a less residual effect.

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